

Dual resonant rectilinear-to-rotary oscillator for broadband electromagnetic energy harvesting with frequency up-conversion

W. Deng and Y. Wang¹

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Stony Brook University, Stony Brook 11790, USA

Abstract

This paper reports a dual resonant rectilinear-to-rotary oscillation converter (RROC) for low frequency broadband electromagnetic energy harvesting from ambient vibrations. An approximate theoretical model has been established to integrate the electromechanical coupling into a comprehensive electromagnetic-dynamic model of the dual resonant RROC. Numerical simulation has proved the nature of dual resonances by revealing that both the rectilinear resonance and the rotary resonance could be achieved when the stand-alone rectilinear oscillator and the stand-alone rotary oscillator were excited independently. Simulation on the magnetically coupled RROC has also shown that the rectilinear resonance and the rotary resonance could be obtained simultaneously in the low-frequency region (2Hz to 14Hz) with well-defined restoring torque (M_r) and the initial rotation angle of the rectilinear oscillator (ψ). The magnetic interaction patterns between the rectilinear and the rotary oscillators have been categorized based on aforementioned simulation results. Both simulation and experimental results have demonstrated broadband output attributing from the dual resonances. Experimental results have also indicated that the RROC could have wide bandwidth in a much lower frequency region (2Hz to 8Hz) even without the rotary resonance as long as the system parameters are carefully tuned. Parameter analysis on different values of M_r and ψ are experimentally carried out to provide a quantitative guidance of designing the RROC to achieve an optimal power density. Studies show that in order to obtain dual resonances in low frequency region (2Hz to 14Hz), ψ should be chosen near 10° and M_r should be chosen with relatively shallow potential wells, which could be easily achieved by adjusting the relative positions of two repulsive magnets. In order to obtain higher-power density and broader bandwidth in a much lower frequency region (2Hz to 8Hz), ψ should be chosen near 0° and M_r should be chosen with relatively shallower potential wells, or ψ could be chosen near 10° and M_r should be chosen with relatively deeper potential wells. Simulation and experimental results have also shown that the electrical damping has little influence on the power output in the frequency region from 2Hz to 8Hz where the rectilinear resonance dominates, while it has significant influence (unfavorable) on the rotary oscillation in the frequency region from 8Hz to 14Hz.

Figure 1. (a) Photo representation of the dual resonant RROC (120 mm OD x 170 mm H), which consists of magnetically coupled RLO (top) and one RTO (bottom). The RTO has a rotor with four arc magnets and a stator with two repulsive rec-

¹ Corresponding author, Ya Wang, Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Stony Brook University
 E-mail address: ya.s.wang@stonybrook.edu (Prof. Ya Wang)

tangular magnets and six coils (2000 turns, 50Ω , one steel screw inside each coil), coupled by a ball bearing. The RLO also has four arc magnets distributed centro-symmetrically; (b) schematic diagram of magnetic coupling of the dual resonant RROC, where $\vec{\mu}_a$ and $\vec{\mu}_b$ refer to the magnetic moment vectors of the RLO magnet, and the rotor magnet, R is distance from the rotor magnet to the rotor center, \vec{r}_{ab} is the vector from the RLO magnet to the rotor magnet, h is the relative translation displacement of the RLO (z axis), θ is the rotation angle of the rotor magnet, ψ is the pre-defined initial angle of the RLO magnet (angle between $\vec{\mu}_a$ and x axis).

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